

Study of the Effect of Guidance and Counselling on Emotions

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Abstract:- 21 st century is the age of information and technology. The need for guidance and advice is felt. It is the power, influence, power and miracle of guidance and advice that it guides and guides man's ability, ability, talent in the right direction. There is a need for guidance and counselling in human childhood, adolescence and adulthood. Its area is wide, social, life, economic, educational, career, personal, religious etc. In need of guidance and counselling.

Keywords:- Guidance, Counselling, Emotions, Development, Class Talk.

I. INTRODUCTION

21st century is the age of information and technology. The need for guidance and advice is felt. It is the power, influence, power and miracle of guidance and advice that it guides and guides man's ability, ability, talent in the right direction. There is a need for guidance and counselling in human childhood, adolescence and adulthood adolescence and adulthood. Its area is wide, social, life, economic, educational, career, personal, religious etc. In need of guidance and counselling. In this research, emphasis has been laid on school guidance and counselling, for the development of emotions, spread at the school level, adapting to the circumstances. Under this there is experimental research, change the emotions, develop, improve, and you can mold yourself.

Statistical Results of Pre-Post Emotional Development of K.V. Secondary Level Students Experimental Group

Emotional Development	Test	Numbers of students	Mean	Standard Deviation	T- Value
Emotional Envelopment -A	Pre	40	61.80	10.30	1.281
	Post	40	58.33	12.13	
Emotional Development - B	Pre	40	63.75	12.60	2.570
	Post	40	57.05	10.64	
Emotional Development	Pre	40	125.55	20.71	2.258
	Post	40	115.38	19.58	

Table 1:- Emotional Development

It is clear from the above table that the mean values of part A and B of emotional development of the experimental group are 125.55 and 115.38 respectively. In order to see the significance of this difference, the T - value of the ratio is

➤ *Research objective:-*

- Preparing - Test Pre and Post Test for Secondary Level Student.
- To prepare the plan of 25 class talk, guidance and counselling program on the impetus to the practical group.
- Administering pre- and post-testing of practical learning.
- To find out the effect of guidance and counselling on emotions on the experimental group.

➤ *Hypothesis -*

There is no significant difference in the effect of guidance and counselling on the pre - post test on the emotions of secondary level students.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

Experimental method will be used in this research. Under which the test was done by pre-post.

➤ *Research Sample*

In the present research, the sample has been selected from **purposeful sampling**, pre-post tests were done on the **40** students of KV.

➤ *Tool/ Device*

In this research, Standards Tool was used - Emotional Ability Development Test Produced by - Nimal Sharma, Dr. V. L. Chouhan, Dr. Ajay Choudhary, Namita Sharma

2.258, which is greater than the fixed value of 0.05 at the degree 40 of independence 1.96. On emotional development. K.V students has a significant impact on secondary level students.

III. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and interpretation of the data, there is a significant effect of guidance and counselling.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Aggarwal, J. C. (2006). Educational Reforms in India for 21st Century. Delhi: Shipra Publications.
- [2]. Bennett, C.D (1993). Professional Helpings and Assisting Students In Education. Education Dissertation, Illinois State University. In Dissertation Abstracts International, Vol.55 (1), July, 1994.
- [3]. Chandra, R. (2005). Guidance and Counselling. Delhi: Kalpez Publications.
- [4]. Crow & Crow (2002). An Introduction to Guidance-Basic Principles and Practice, Sec. Ed. Surjeet Publication, Delhi.

➤ *Web Sites*

- [5]. www.ncert.nic.in
- [6]. www.aiscap.nic.in
- [7]. www.rci.nic.in